

1 **A PIECE OF THE ECOTOXICOLOGY PUZZLE: HOW CAN CURRENT AND FUTURE**
2 **RESEARCH INFORM PPD REGULATIONS?**
3 **EVALUATING THE EFFECTS OF TIRE POLLUTANTS 6PPD AND 6PPD-Q AND**
4 **SUGGESTING FUTURE RESEARCH ROUTES TO FILL THE GAPS: AN EXTENSIVE**
5 **REVIEW COVERING SPECIES-SPECIFIC AND INTRACELLULAR TOXIC REPERCUSSIONS**

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47 **Abstract**

48 2-((4-Methylpentan-2-yl)amino)-5-(phenylamino)cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione
49 commonly known as 6PPD-Quinone (6PPD-Q), is the ozonized derivative of, N-(1,3-
50 dimethylbutyl)-N'-phenyl-p-phenylenediamine, 6PPD. 6PPD is a common tire coating that acts

51 as an antioxidant by preventing rubber degradation by acting as an antioxidant. Research
52 efforts elucidating 6PPD-Q's toxicity surged after a 2021 study identified 6PPD-Q as an acute
53 mortality inducing toxicant to coho salmon. This commentary functions as a compilation of
54 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's interaction with aquatic and terrestrial organisms. We also encompass
55 studies providing toxicological explanations of dysregulation of intracellular activity such as
56 transcription and metabolite transformation. ~~We~~ This review aims to concurrently impart an
57 overview of the most current 6PPD and 6PPD-Q studies at organismal and cellular levels,
58 emphasize research gaps, such as the lack of global EPA regulations, and propose possible
59 routes for future studies, like the expansion into different model organisms, lifecycle effects,
60 fertility and transgenerational effects, and cancer cell studies, and various research routes.

61 Introduction

62 For years, freshwater environments have been experiencing "urban stream syndrome," a
63 phenomenon attributed to the increased environmental pollutants altering water quality.¹ In
64 urbanized areas, road runoff is a contributing factor to the decline in freshwater habitats. Coho
65 salmon dwell in freshwater streams, typically near highly urbanized areas. Pacific salmon, more
66 specifically coho salmon, are integral to the diverse connection between saltwater and
67 freshwater food webs.¹ However, coho salmon have been experiencing acute mortality rates
68 when migrating to freshwater ecosystems to reproduce. In 2021, *N*-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-*N'*-
69 phenyl-*p*-phenylenediamine-quinone, 6PPD-Quinone (6PPD-Q), was identified as the main
70 contributor to the acute mortality rate seen in coho salmon.²

71 While this discovery is recent, its precursor 6PPD, was originally discovered in the
72 1960s. 6PPD falls within a class of compounds called *p*-phenylenediamine (PPD) which are
73 used as antiozonant coatings on rubber tires to prevent breakdown and prolong usage.⁴
74 Because of its properties, 6PPD quickly became the gold standard for tire antiozonants (Figure
75 1). Since then, there have been no alternative antiozonants that match 6PPDs ability to prevent
76 rubber breakdown.

77 As transportation methods evolve so does the way we combat wear and tear on tires. In
78 the rubber industry, the lifetime of a tire is a big concern. Chemicals compounds in the such as
79 *p*-phenylenediamine (PPD) are a class of antioxidant and antiozonant molecules used to
80 coat tires to prevent breakdown and prolong their usage.³ Molecules in the PPD class are
81 considered highly reactive. When originally discovered in the 1960s, 6PPD, *N*-(1,3-
82 dimethylbutyl)-*N'*-phenyl-*p*-phenylenediamine, quickly became the gold standard antiozonant
83 (Figure 1). As of today, there are no alternative antiozonant tire coatings available or in use.

84 As such, 6PPD has become a prominent environmental pollutant in recent years. When
85 entering the environment, 6PPD can react with ozone creating *N*-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-*N'*-phenyl-
86 *p*-phenylenediamine-quinone, (6PPD-Quinone (6PPD-Q) (Figure 2).⁴ Quinones, when
87 introduced *in vivo*, can induce cytotoxicity, immunotoxicity, or activate detoxification enzymes,
88 depending on their reactivity.⁵

89 Both these two molecules, are ubiquitous and areas ubiquitous as they are, readily enter the
90 environment through road run-off, rubber waste, and dust, accumulating dust and
91 accumulating in both rural and urban waterways (Supplemental Figure 1 and Supplemental
92 Table 1). Table 1). The half-life of 6PPD is approximately 5 hours in water compared to 6PPD-Q
93 which has a half-life of about 33 hours.⁶ Although the half-lives of both chemicals are relatively
94 short, the amount of tires on the road at any given time contribute to the continual leaching of
95 PPDs into waterways. Additionally, even small amounts of PPDs, in the ng/L range, can lead to
96 mortality among aquatic wildlife. This indicates high reactivity. Thus, continued long-term
97 usage of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q has raised concern for aquatic life subjected to these chemicals.

98 As more information surrounding 6PPD is published, a trend of mortality in coho salmon
99 has become apparent. Coho salmon dwell in freshwater streams, typically near highly urbanized
100 areas.⁷ As these urban areas expand, more road runoff is produced leading to detrimental
101 effects in aquatic habitats nearby streams. Increased mortality rates of coho salmon required

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102 deeper investigation that led to the discovery of PPDs as an environmental toxicant.
103 Furthermore, coho salmon seem to be more sensitive to PPDs unlike other freshwater species.
104 The accumulation of PPDs seem to impact coho salmon at higher rates than other freshwater
105 species. The coho salmon mortality discovery has opened the door to a new field in
106 ecotoxicology environmental toxicant research. Slowly, more publications have revealed
107 species, like zebrafish specifically, with higher tolerances to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.^{6,8-18}
108 Additionally, other species and *in vitro* models, when exposed to PPDs, have exhibited
109 metabolic changes and dysregulated genes.^{4,10,22-26} Studies investigating PPD exposure the
110 effects in humans living in areas with high rubber recycling reported similar changes to
111 metabolism.¹⁹⁻²³ as well as metabolites and transcriptional changes in species and cell lines
112 when exposed to PPDs.^{6,12,24-28}

113 Though impacts of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are widespread, there are no global regulations
114 against PPD usage. The United States Environmental Protection Agency, USEPA, is supplying
115 funding to expand the understanding of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's impact and has developed an
116 action plan to mitigate the risks.^{29,30} The United States has completed initial aquatic life
117 screenings to discern the acute exposure levels for 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, 8.9 µg/L and 11 ng/L,
118 respectively.^{31,32} Comparatively, the Canadian Environmental Protection Agency, CEPA, has
119 added PPDs to their substance priority list and are working towards possibly implementing a
120 ban.³³ The European Union's Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of
121 Chemicals, REACH, is also considering employing restrictions of 6PPD use.³⁴ Whichever
122 country or region can amass sufficient research to support and implement their own regulations
123 will likely help direct other global regulations.

124 Although other 6PPD reviews and commentaries have been published covering
125 environmental impacts on individual species, this our commentary aims to summarize what is
126 known thus far about the toxic effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q in multiple aquatic organisms,
127 model organisms, and human cell lines.³⁵⁻³⁹ To aid in comparisons between species and cell
128 lines, conversions of environmental concentrations (µg/L) of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q to molar
129 concentrations are provided for reference (Supplemental Table 2) displayed in Supplemental
130 Table 2. What is known about 6PPD, and 6PPD-Q's biological impact across organisms is
131 lacking, especially when testing environmentally relevant concentrations and employing similar
132 experimental designs scarce with only a few discoveries agreeing between studies. We aim to
133 point out the gap controversy occurring within the 6PPD and 6PPD-Q research domain and
134 provide suggestions to drive scientific discovery, and understanding, and regulations. Our
135 recommendations include, transgenerational studies, toxicological impacts on female model
136 organisms, epigenetics, implementation of fungal models, fate of PPD metabolites, toxicity to
137 cancer cells, single cell sequencing, and co-exposure of environmental toxicants.

138 Major gaps regarding EPA regulation, detection of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q in the environment, non-
139 aquatic model organisms, and limited research in cell lines need to be addressed. To remedy
140 these missing pieces of the puzzle, the underlying toxic mechanism of PPDs needs to be
141 uncovered to better understand ways to combat their toxicity.

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Figure 1. Timeline of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q development, implementation, and toxic nature (created using BioRender.com).

Figure 2. Transformation of 6PPD to 6PPD-Q in the presence of ozone (O_3) (created using BioRender.com).

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Table 1. Countries with 6PPD and/or 6PPD-Q detected in local samples.

Country	Location of Sample Site	Chemical	References
Argentina	Buenos Aires	6PPD-Q	[40]
Australia	Queensland (Brisbane River)	6PPD-Q	[41,42]
Brazil	São Paulo	6PPD-Q	[40]
Canada	Southern Ontario (Don River and Highland Creek) and Toronto	6PPD-Q	[40,43-45]
Chile	Santiago	6PPD-Q	[40]
China	Guangzhou (Liuxi River and Guanghua Basin), South China (Greater Bay Area), Guangdong (Pearl River and Dongjiang river), Zhejiang (Zhujiang river and Jiaojiang River), Yangtze River, Taiyuan, Zhengzhou, Shanghai, Nanjing, Hangzhou, and Hong Kong	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	[26,46-57]
Colombia	Bogeta	6PPD-Q	[40]
Germany	Leipzig Saxony	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	[58-61]
India	Kolkata and New Delhi	6PPD-Q	[40]
Japan	Tokyo	6PPD-Q	[40,62]
Nigeria	Lagos	6PPD-Q	[40]
Poland	Warsaw	6PPD-Q	[40]
Spain	Madrid	6PPD-Q	[40]

USA California (San Francisco Bay), Colorado, Georgia, Kansas, Michigan, Minnesota, Mississippi (Oxford), New York, North Carolina, Oklahoma, Oregon, Texas, Virginia, and Washington (Tacoma) 6PPD-Q [40,63–66]

152 Table 12. Common concentrations of 6PPD* and 6PPD-Q* listed as micrograms per liter (µg/L)
153 and corresponding conversion to nanomolar (nM).

6PPD (µg/L)	6PPD (nM)	6PPD-Q (µg/L)	6PPD-Q (nM)
0.1	0.370	0.1	0.340
5	1.86	5	1.68
40	3.73	40	3.35
50	18.6	50	16.8
100	37.3	100	33.5
500	186	500	167.6
4000	373	4000	335

154 *Based on molar masses 6PPD, 268.4 g/mol and 6PPD-Q, 298.4 g/mol

156 Methods

157 To gather data, we used the National Library of Medicine (NIH) search engine PubMed.
158 For example, we used keywords, 6PPD, 6PPD-Q, zebrafish, coho salmon, and *Caenorhabditis*
159 *elegans* to identify how many papers had been published within this field of study. To further
160 narrow our search, we included combinations of keywords into our searches such as “6PPD,
161 zebrafish.” We then sorted through each paper to determine which area of study the paper
162 focused on and if the information fit into the focus of our manuscript. We were unable to employ
163 any time restrictions to our searches because all relevant research has been published within
164 the last five years. Any paper published and available through PubMed was considered for our
165 commentary.

167 Aquatic Organisms

168 4. Coho Salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*) and the lethal effects of PPDs (To what 169 extent are coho salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*) affected by 6PPD-Q?

170 Many efforts have been made to thoroughly investigate the consequences of
171 environmental pollutant 6PPD-Q ~~in~~ ~~the~~ ~~surfactant~~ ~~particles~~ on coho salmon. Coho salmon are of
172 high ecological importance because of well-documented “coho pre-spawn mortality” of adult
173 coho salmon returning to spawn. A 2021 study was the first to evaluate mortality in coho salmon
174 following “recognition” of the ecological phenomenon (Table 13).² Researchers used juvenile
175 coho salmon as a stand-in representative ~~for~~ ~~of~~ adult coho salmon. 6PPD-Q was found to be
176 highly toxic with the mean lethal concentration being $0.79 \pm 0.16 \mu\text{g/L}$ after only 2 to 6 hours of
177 exposure. Following this report, efforts have been made to investigate toxicity at all coho salmon
178 life stages. Coho salmon embryos have been tested for growth and survival effects following

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179 6PPD-Q exposure. Multiple 6PPD-Q exposures found significant embryonic mortality observed
180 at 7.22 µg/L, as 79 percent of treated embryos failed to hatch. In addition, 21 percent of the
181 treated embryos exhibited significant adverse development and growth.² In a different study,
182 three week old juveniles had a median LC50 of 41.0 ng/L after 24 hours of constant exposure.⁶⁷
183 ~~In a~~ An adult coho salmon study, found acute mortality was found to be induced at a slightly
184 higher concentration of 1.3 to 1.8 µg/L 6PPD-Q.⁶⁸ Taken altogether, these findings indicate that
185 even within species, the tolerance level of 6PPD-Q varies depending on life stage. This
186 presents the need to continually implement the assessment of species' progressional life stages
187 into toxicology studies. Confirming lethal concentrations for embryonic to adult populations will
188 help inform regulations and preserve sensitive species' populations.

189 Both behavioral and physiological changes were also induced. Exposed salmon
190 exhibited changes in behavior ranging from lethargy to complete immobilization. Physiological
191 blood parameters indicated a significant increase in hematocrit, percentage of red blood cells,
192 suggesting cardiorespiratory distress.⁶⁹ Most recently, coho salmon embryos have also been
193 tested for growth and survival effects following 6PPD-Q exposure. Multiple 6PPD-Q exposures
194 found significant embryonic mortality was observed at 7.22 µg/L, as 79 percent of treated
195 embryos failed to hatch. Additionally, 21 percent of the treated embryos exhibited significant
196 adverse development and growth.⁴ Though scientists have reached coordinating conclusions
197 regarding the mortality effects of 6PPD-Q in coho salmon, knowledge gaps concerning
198 behavioral, morphological, and physiological effects throughout the life cycle remain. Research
199 efforts have instead trended towards expanding upon 6PPD-Q effects on other aquatic
200 organisms.

201 **2. Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*)**

202 **a. Morphological changes in Zebrafish (this section heading needs reworking)**

203 ~~maybe~~ How does the mortality rate in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) compare to coho salmon?

204 Like coho salmon, Zzebrafish embryos and larvae are a popular model organism being
205 used to investigate the effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q because they are considered a "tolerant"
206 species.¹⁶ Their short gestational times and transparent bodies make morphological studies
207 simple and accessible. Several studies have expanded upon 6PPD-Q's effect on coho salmon
208 by testing environmental levels of both PPD compounds on used zebrafish, to examine effects
209 of environmental levels of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. In three studies, treatment of 6PPD and its
210 quinone derivative induce various morphological transformations and mortality rates in zebrafish
211 (Table 13). Depending on the method of exposure and analysis, the lethal concentrations of
212 PPDs can vary. Using zebrafish embryos, one study maintained stable concentrations of 6PPD
213 and 6PPD-Q for 96 hours. They then estimated the lethal concentrations to be 442.62 µg/L and
214 132.92 µg/L respectively.⁸ When exposed to stable concentrations of 6PPD for 120 hours the
215 tolerance increased. This was confirmed using UPLC-QE. The measured LC50 was 0.87 mg/L
216 6PPD and no significant effect was found upon treatment of 6PPD-Q up to 10 mg/L.¹⁸ It is
217 important to note the aforementioned studies differ in experimental design, data acquisition, and
218 analysis making comparisons between LC50 values difficult. Compared to coho salmon the lack
219 of acute toxicity in zebrafish tends to label them as "tolerant," however, since the LC50 values
220 vary so greatly depending on methodology, the definitive categorization of zebrafish may be
221 more nuanced. In 2022, Vashney et. al. 2022, discovered the lethal concentration at 96 hr for
222 6PPD and 6PPD-Q in zebrafish to be 442.62 µg/L and 132.92 µg/L respectively.⁸ This has been
223 contradicted more recently in 2024 when Chang et. al published a 120-hour LC50 of 870 µg/L for
224 6PPD.¹⁸ This is a stark increase in concentration at a longer exposure time compared to what
225 was previously published. Additionally, the more recent study failed to mention the lethal
226 concentration for 6PPD-Q, adding to the discrepancies between scientific findings. The effect of
227 6PPD across various studies at different concentrations have varied but all have reported some
228 morphological changes.

229 **How do PPDs affect zebrafish morphology, behavior, and physiology?**

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230 The reasoning for zebrafish's classification as "tolerant," extends beyond the lethal
231 concentration as PPDs also affect morphology, behavior, and physiology. Morphologically,
232 across various studies using differing concentration ranges 6PPD caused a decrease in eye
233 development and eye size, hatchability, body length, and reduced swim bladder size. Multiple
234 studies have observed morphological alterations. Variable 6PPD concentrations resulted in
235 decreases in eye development and eye size, hatchability, body length, and swim bladder
236 size.^{8,10,13,14,18} Between the studies there is discrepancy/controversy over the effects of 6PPD on
237 hatchability and body length. Additionally, Comparatively, in zebrafish exposed to a range of
238 6PPD-Q concentrations, there are had no significant changes to eye or bladder development.
239 However, but zebrafish had increased instances of reduced eye size, lordosis, kyphosis, and
240 malformations of the tail.^{8,14,18} While decrease in eye size is consistent between both chemicals,
241 other morphological effects indicate a difference in 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's biological targets.
242 The foundation of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's impact has been laid however, additional studies
243 covering the lethal concentration and morphological effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q should be
244 conducted to fully understand the extent of effects.

245 **b. Behavioral changes**

246 Along with morphological changes, 6PPD also altered zebrafish behavior and
247 physiological conditions. After 96 hours of exposure to 25 µg/L 6PPD, zebrafish larvae
248 experienced a decrease in total swim distance, angular swim velocity and heart rate (BPM).
249 Zebrafish also experienced a dose-dependent increase in oxygen consumption.⁸ Likewise, a
250 different study discovered after 120 hours of exposure to 0.4 mg/L zebrafish larvae had inhibited
251 phototactic behavior.⁶⁹ Between these two studies, 6PPD caused altered behavior and
252 interfered with normal physiological processes. These alterations are likely closely associated
253 with the morphological abnormalities previously discussed.

254 Similarly, 6PPD-Q also induced altered behavior and interfered with physiological
255 processes. When exposed to 10 and 25 µg/L 6PPD-Q for 96 hours zebrafish exhibited
256 decreased total swim distance and angular swim velocity.⁸ A different study showcased the
257 same decrease in total swim distance using a higher concentration of 6PPD-Q, 50 µg/L, and an
258 extended exposure time of 120 hours.¹⁰ Additionally, a third study used low doses of 20, 200
259 ng/L, and 2000 ng/L over a 24 hour period and observed decreased locomotive activity and
260 increased sleeping bouts during daylight cycles.¹⁶ Taken together, both PPDs cause significant
261 morphological, behavioral, and physiological changes in zebrafish. Even "tolerant" species are
262 experiencing adverse symptoms when exposed to PPDs further exacerbating the need to
263 implement global regulations.

264 Building off of the morphological changes, behavior has also been reported to be
265 differentially affected by 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.^{8,10,16,18} Zebrafish have also been used to study
266 behavioral changes when exposed to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. The virtual motor response (VMR)
267 and vibrational startle response (VSR) were not affected in the presence of 6PPD-Q but
268 significant changes were observed in the sleep-wake cycle when subjected to light-dark
269 cycles.¹⁸ Zebrafish, when exposed to 2 µg/L of 6PPD-Q, had increased frequency of sleeping
270 bouts and slept more frequently throughout the light periods.¹⁶ Moreover, the phototactic
271 behavioral response of zebrafish, behavior in response to light, was significantly decreased
272 when exposed to 6PPD but not 6PPD-Q.¹⁸ These changes in behavior are likely linked to
273 physiological changes induced by 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. Additional studies are needed to address
274 the differences between the effects of the two chemicals.

275 **c. Physiological changes in Zebrafish**

276 Aside from morphological and behavioral changes induced by PPDs, zebrafish also
277 have shown various physiological changes, some even linking to the changes in behavior. Both

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278 toxicants 6PPD and 6PPD-Q affect heart rate, cardiac output, oxygen consumption, hormone
279 levels and regulation of neurotransmitters, and hormone levels. Both 6PPD, 25 µg/L, and 6PPD-
280 Q, 10 and 25 µg/L, cause a decrease in heart rate and blood oxygen levels in zebrafish.⁸ A
281 different study concluded that upon exposure to 0.02 µg/L 6PPD-Q there is a significant
282 increase in heart rate but no difference in oxygen levels consumption.¹⁶ This difference is likely
283 due to experimental design. Between the two studies the treatment concentrations vary over
284 1000 fold. This is important to note when considering the environmental concentrations typically
285 seen and comparison of biological effects. Within the same study there is further controversy
286 about the up and down regulation of neurotransmitters. Ricarte et. al, Two studies investigated
287 the effects of 6PPD-Q on neurotransmitters norepinephrine and dopamine, both essential for
288 motor functions. Additionally, the same study found that Treatment of 0.02 µg/L 6PPD-Q
289 increases the levels of norepinephrine while not changing dopamine levels.¹⁶ can be
290 seen in dopamine. This phenomena was contradicted in A different study that found 50 µg/L
291 6PPD-Q decreases dopamine and does not affect norepinephrine levels.¹⁰ Again between the
292 comparative studies the experimental design varies, likely contributing to the differences
293 however the conclusion is the same, 6PPD-Q negatively effects neurotransmitters involved in
294 motor function., concentrations used to study hormone levels vary over 1000 fold. The
295 controversy continues in regard to thyroid function. 6PPD has been found to significantly
296 increase the levels of T4 without altering the levels of T3.¹⁸ These findings differ from Peng et.
297 al, who found that 6PPD causes a decrease in levels of T3.¹⁴ T3 and T4 are influential
298 hormones in eye development in zebrafish which are affected by 6PPD. This coincides with the
299 claims that 6PPD and 6PPD-Q can cause morphological eye changes. The differences in
300 morphological changes linked with neurotransmitter and hormone expression need to be further
301 studied to determine the underlying mechanism of toxicity. These differential findings emphasize
302 the need for further studies confirming or negating the effects of PPDs on physiological changes
303 in zebrafish.

304 Terrestrial Organisms and the effects of PPDs How are Terrestrial Organisms affected by 305 PPDs?

306 1. Mice (*Mus musculus*)

307 Toxic effects of 6PPD-Q have also started to be studied in mammalian models such as
308 male mice and rats. Male mice offer a good fertility model because of their short reproductive
309 times. 6PPD-Q has been found to be reproductively toxic, metabolically and inflammation
310 inducing to male mice (Table 3) Across many studies, 6PPD-Q has been found to complicate
311 reproductive processes and induce inflammation responses (Table 1).⁷⁰⁻⁷⁶ In one study, when
312 When subjected to injected with 4 mg/kg 6PPD-Q, mouse testosterone levels decreased and
313 sperm quality declined, as well as the quality of sperm. This led to complications in *in vitro*
314 fertilization (IVF) and suggests impaired male fertility.⁷⁵ decreasing male fertility and impairing
315 IVF declined which is needed for successful *in vitro* fertilization (IVF), this suggested impaired
316 male fertility.⁷⁵ Additionally, pathways involving spermatogenesis and sphingolipid metabolism
317 were differentially affected.⁽⁷⁵⁾ after exposure to 4 mg/kg 6PPD-Q for 40 days at 4 mg/kg.⁷⁵

318 Furthermore, multiple studies observed fluctuations in inflammation responses. Two
319 studies employed different methods of 6PPD-Q exposure on two mouse models. The first
320 injected 10 and 100 µg/kg/ for 21 days and the second injected one dose of 4 mg/kg and
321 monitored response over one week. Both saw an increase in the inflammatory cytokines, TNF-
322 α, IL-1, IL-6, and IL-10.^{71,72} At even doses, 10 and 100 µg/kg/day of injected 6PPD-Q caused
323 intestinal and lung inflammation, in the ileum and jejunum, in mice, which was further confirmed
324 by increased levels of TNF-α, IL-1, and IL-6, and IL-10 inflammatory cytokines.⁷²
325 Other Additional inflammatory cytokines, TNF-α, IL-10 and IL-6, were observed in the lungs of
326 male BALB/c mice after repeated injection of 6PPD-Q in a bioaccumulation study.⁷⁴ A third
327 study injected mice exposed male C57BL/6 mice to with 0.4 and 4 mg/kg 6PPD-Q every
328 4 days for a over a 28 day prolonged period and saw similar increases in inflammatory

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329 cytokines. They also discovered apoptosis, blood-brain barrier disruption, and increased levels
330 of reactive oxygen species (ROS). levels increased, increased levels of ROS, apoptosis, and
331 blood-brain barrier disruption.⁷³

332 6PPD-Q has also been found to contribute to hepatotoxicity in mice in male mice and
333 rats. Long term exposure for 21 days via the oral route, (0.1 and 1 µg/kg bw per day) to 6PPD-Q
334 led to elevated lipid deposition in the liver which can contribute to metabolic dysfunction-
335 associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD),⁷⁴ and short term exposure affected glucose and
336 riboflavin, essential for liver health, and metabolism.⁷⁴ These selected mice and rat studies
337 highlight the various toxic effects of 6PPD-Q. There is still a major research gap including
338 female mice and rat models as well as exposure to 6PPD. Because of the wide effects of 6PPD-
339 Q, additional studies focusing on these areas would improve our need to be implemented to
340 push the understanding of the toxic mechanisms of both PPDs 6PPD and 6PPD-Q allowing for
341 better informed policy and regulations for mammalian benefit.

342 2. Humans (*Homo sapiens*)

343 To better understand the effects of 6PPD and its quinone derivative on human health
344 populations, epidemiology studies were carried out in areas with high electronic and rubber
345 waste disposal. Specifically, in industrialized China, children from ages 2 to 7 underwent urine
346 analysis to detect PPDs and results were compared to a control group located farther from the
347 waste disposal site. The median levels of PPDs, 6PPD 0.073 and 6PPD-Q 2.34 ng/mL, were
348 higher for the group in closer proximity to the waste plant.¹⁹ Dust samples from houses,
349 kindergartens, and road areas with high levels of rubber recycling were compared to a control
350 and for houses and kindergartens the concentration of 6PPD-Q was also exhibited higher
351 concentrations urine concentrations of 6PPD-Q, 3.2 and 7.5 ng/g respectively.²¹ The same
352 study also investigated the presence of polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs),
353 polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), and heavy metal(loid)s, (Ni and Cu) in kindergarten dust
354 samples.

355 These toxicants are thought to be was further associated with a decrease in body mass index
356 (BMI), alteration of the gut microbiota, and more frequent illnesses such as influenza in areas
357 with high rubber recycling compared to areas with low rubber recycling (Table 13),^{20,21} Ingestion
358 of dust in toddlers, approximately 3.48 ng/kg bw/d, was also tracked to indoor venues through
359 paint and flooring materials.²² Although the main focus this far has been on 6PPD's effects in
360 children, one study detected the toxicants PPDs in breastmilk and adult urine.²³ This raises
361 concerns that these tire pollutants may be passing from parent to child. Currently, there are no
362 regulations for acceptable daily intake (ADI) or tolerable daily intake (TDI) for 6PPD or 6PPD-Q.
363 More studies encompassing dust exposure, human excretions, co-exposure with other
364 toxicants, and transgenerational transmission in multiple world regions will give greater insight
365 on exposure level so a tolerance level can be established.

366 3. *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*)

367 While 6PPD-Q is often confirmed to be in freshwater environments, rivers, creeks, and
368 seas, it has also been found in dirt and air samples. *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*) offer
369 unique insight upon 6PPD-Q exposure as they are often terrestrial, but can also be found in
370 aquatic environments. Investigating mortality in nematodes revealed only a 5 percent mortality
371 rate when subjected to 100 µg/L 6PPD-Q (Table 1). It was noted that the mortality level was
372 nowhere near complete sample mortality but was still significant when compared to the control
373 group.⁷⁷ Though mortality is uncommon in *C. elegans*, three studies found 6PPD-Q exposure
374 resulted in a decreased lifespan.⁷⁸⁻⁸⁰

375 Like zebrafish, behavioral changes also appear in *C. elegans*. Two studies found
376 treatment of lower 6PPD-Q concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 10 µg/L resulted in decreased
377 and abnormal locomotion.⁸¹ Decreased locomotion was hypothesized to be caused by the
378 neurodegeneration observed in D-type neurons following exposure to 10 µg/L 6PPD-Q.⁸²
379 Neurodegeneration was also observed in dopaminergic, glutamatergic, serotonergic, and

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380 GABAergic neurons causing decreased sensory perception and neurotransmission.⁸¹
 381 Comparatively, *in vivo*, exposure to 1 to 10 µg/L 6PPD-Q resulted in a decrease of dopamine
 382 synthesis leading to a decrease of dopamine related behavior.⁸² Therefore, 6PPD-Q seems to
 383 be a neurotoxin, targeting a multitude of neurons and inhibiting normal behavior.

384 No morphological changes were indicated in any *C. elegans* studies, however, metabolic
 385 and inflammatory responses were prevalent. Increased intestinal permeability was found in
 386 nematodes exposed to treated with 1 to 10 µg/L 6-PPD-Q.^{77,83} Metabolism appears to be
 387 broadly affected as an increase in fatty acid synthesis resulted in lipid accumulation. Glycogen
 388 and glucose metabolism were also inversely affected as 6PPD-Q exposure resulted in an
 389 increase of glycogen metabolism and a decrease of glucose metabolism.⁸⁴⁻⁸⁷ Each of these
 390 responses across multiple studies indicates the widespread toxic effects of 6PPD-Q. Moving
 391 forward, continuing to study metabolic changes in *C. elegans* will lead to a better understanding
 392 of 6PPD-Q's biological targets and allow for better informed regulations.
 393 Recent research has trended towards studying changes in metabolism within *C. elegans*, which
 394 is integral to identifying biotransformations and potential exposure markers, however, many
 395 more metabolic pathways stand to be studied.

396
 397 Table 13. Summary of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q effect on aquatic organisms animals, terrestrial
 398 organisms animals, and humans. High effect level indicates mortality at concentrations <100
 399 µg/L 6PPD or 6PPD-Q with severe deformities, and organ dysfunction. Moderate effect level
 400 indicates mortality induced at concentrations ≥100 µg/L 6PPD or 6PPD-Q, and/or physiological
 401 and behavioral impairment. Low effect level indicates mild or nonlethal effects, and/or limited
 402 biological impacts. *Differences in LC50 values are likely due to differences in experimental
 403 design.

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	Chemical treated	LC50	Effect Level	Biological Effects	Findings	References
Coho Salmon	6PPD-Q	Embryonic 7.22 µg/L Juvenile* 0.79 µg/L, 41.0 ng/L, 95 ng/L Adult 100 mg/L	High	Mortality induced in embryonic (LC50 of 7.22 µg/L), juvenile (LC50 of 0.79 µg/L, 41.0 ng/L and 95 ng/L)*, and adult forms (LC50 of 100 mg/L) Morphological: decreased size Behavioral: lethargy and immobilization Physiological: increased hematocrit	Decreased size, increased hematocrit	[2,4,67,68]
Zebra fish	6PPD and 6PPD-Q of	96 hr LC50	Moderate	Mortality induced Morphological:	Decreased eye size, hatchability,	[8,10,13,14,16,18]

6PPD-Q 132.92 µg/L, 96 hr LC50 6PPD of 442.62 µg/L and 2.2 mg/L, 120 hr IC50 6PPD of 0.87 mg/L*

~~decreased eye development and size, hatchability, body length, and swim bladder size~~
Behavioral: decreased swimming abilities, increased sleeping, and decreased phototactic behavioral response
Physiological: altered affect heart rate, cardiac output, oxygen consumption, hormone levels and regulation of neurotransmitters

body length and swim bladder, decreased swimming and phototactic response, increased sleeping, altered heart rate, cardiac output, oxygen consumption, and hormone and neurotransmitters

Rotifer 6PPD-Q ???

Moderate to low

Mortality and decreased population growth

Decreased population size

[⁸⁸]

Brook Trout 6PPD-Q Fry = 0.2 µg/L Fingerlings = 0.5 mg/L

High

Acute mortality, Physiological: increased interlamellar cell mass (ILCM) size, hematocrit, blood glucose, and total CO₂
Decreased blood sodium and chloride concentration

Increased interlamellar cell mass (ILCM) size, hematocrit, blood glucose, and total CO₂. Decreased blood sodium and chloride concentration

[⁸⁹]

Rainbow Trout 6PPD-Q 1.00 µg/L and 2.08 µg/L*

High

Acute mortality, Physiological: increased cardiorespiratory, respiration, and metabolism

Increased cardiorespiration, respiration, and metabolism

[^{90,91}]

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Arctic Char	6PPD-Q	<u>N/A</u>	<u>Low</u>	Physiological: <u>increased metabolism</u>	<u>Increased metabolism</u>	[⁹⁰]
Lake Trout	6PPD-Q	<u>96 hr = 0.50 µg/L</u>	<u>High</u>	Acute mortality, Morphological: Caudal fin and eye deformities	<u>Caudal fin and eye deformities</u>	[⁹²]
Mice	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	<u>N/A</u>	<u>Moderate</u>	Physiological: <u>Decreased testosterone, sperm quality, Altered spermatogenesis, and sphingolipid metabolism pathways</u> Increased inflammation and lipid accumulation	<u>Decreased testosterone, sperm quality, altered spermatogenesis, and sphingolipid metabolism pathways.</u> <u>Increased inflammation and lipid accumulation</u>	[⁷¹⁻⁷⁵]
Humans	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	<u>N/A</u>	<u>Moderate</u>	Physiological: <u>decreased BMI, altered gut microbiome, and increased susceptibility to illnesses</u>	<u>Decreased BMI, altered gut microbiome, and increased susceptibility to illnesses</u>	[¹⁹⁻²³]
C. Elegans	6PPD-Q	<u>100 µg/L</u>	<u>Moderate</u>	Moderate lethality, Behavioral: <u>altered locomotion</u> Physiological: <u>increased intestinal permeability, neurodegeneration, lipid accumulation, and glycogen metabolism.</u> Decreased glucose metabolism and dopamine synthesis	<u>Altered locomotion, increased intestinal permeability, neurodegeneration, lipid accumulation and glycogen metabolism.</u> <u>Decreased glucose metabolism and dopamine synthesis</u>	[^{77-87,93}]

405 **What is known about the metabolic fate of PPDs and their interactions with proteins?**

406 The metabolic fate of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q is still largely unknown. PPDs have been
407 studied in *in vivo* and *in vitro* models including zebrafish, mice, human and rat liver microsomes,
408 rainbow trout liver cells (RTL-W1), and human liver cell lines (L02 and HepG2).^{6,12,24,25,27,28} A
409 short half-life of a toxicant showcases the need to identify potential biomarkers in the
410 transformation products (TPs). For example in mice, the half-life of 6PPD-Q in blood, urine, and
411 feces were identified to be 5.32, 6.20, and 3.87 hours respectively.²⁸ When studying
412 transformation products of toxicants, typically transformations are labeled as Phase I and Phase
413 II metabolites with subsequent modifications. Across species, the TPs may vary depending on
414 the metabolic pathways used to detoxify 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. Two transformations of 6PPD-Q,
415 hydroxylation and glucuronidation, have been identified across species as common
416 metabolites.^{6,12,24,27,28,94} Likewise, the most common transformation of 6PPD is hydroxylation.⁶
417 Thorough research has indicated strong potential for hydroxylation and glucuronidation TPs to
418 act as effective biomarkers for 6PPD-Q exposure, further investigation is needed to identify
419 possible biomarkers for 6PPD's metabolism.

420 Several studies have identified cytochrome p450 enzymes, CYP1A, CYP3A, 3A4, and
421 2C19, as integral to the metabolic breakdown of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.^{24,25,95} When CYP1A was
422 inhibited by α -naphthoflavone (ANF) and quercetin, the levels of unmetabolised 6PPD-Q
423 increased, indicating its enzymatic activity is imperative.²⁵ Beyond interacting with metabolic
424 enzymes, PPDs also interact with proteins affiliated with blood, neurons, and cancer. Molecular
425 docking has confirmed 6PPD and 6PPD-Q forms complexes with human serum albumin (HSA),
426 alters the secondary structure, and differentially affects the esterase activity.⁹⁶ 6PPD-Q has also
427 been shown to interact with neuronal proteins involved in neurotransmitter reception and
428 synthesis, for example BAS-1, GLB-10, and acetylcholinesterase.^{81,82,97} These interactions are
429 likely the basis for the neurotoxicity seen in the presence of 6PPD-Q. Molecular docking has
430 also uncovered 6PPD-Q's potential effect on prostate cancer signaling pathway proteins.
431 Normally, JAK2 is involved in regulating the cell cycle, but since it has strong binding affinity
432 with 6PPD-Q, this has implications regarding the metastasis of prostate cancer.⁹⁸ Taken
433 together, the metabolic breakdown and widespread protein interactions of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q
434 complicate our full understanding of their toxicological implications. We believe not addressing
435 these complications may prevent progress in policy making. As stated, solidifying metabolic
436 biomarkers for both PPDs is the first step towards understanding how these toxicants interact *in*
437 *vivo* and *in vitro*.

438
439 **How do PPDs affect gene regulation prior to the inflammatory response?**

440 Current research indicates a trend in 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's proclivity to prompt an
441 organism's immune response, primarily via the organism's inflammation pathway.
442 We aim to distinguish differences in an organism's gene regulation seen leading up to, during,
443 and after the inflammatory response.

444 Prior to inducing an inflammatory response, PPDs create a stressful environment that
445 results in cellular oxidative damage. This is characterized by an elevation of ROS levels. Many
446 studies directly measured ROS levels following 6PPD treatment and found an increase in ROS
447 in embryonic, larval, and adult zebrafish.^{7,11,12,104-106} In comparison, 6PPD-Q was found to

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448 induce oxidative stress within human liver cell lines like L02 and HepG2 as well as in *C. elegans*
449 and mice.^{25,72,76,82,110,111.}

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450 To further confirm the presence of increased ROS following PPD treatment, researchers
451 have analyzed the regulation of antioxidant genes responsible for mediating oxidative stress like
452 SOD-2, SOD-3, and SOD-4. Two studies found increased expression of antioxidant genes,
453 further indicating oxidative stress is caused by PPDs.^{76,97} *C. elegans*, tend to employ the
454 mitochondrial unfolded protein response (mt UPR) in the presence of oxidative stress.
455 Specifically, this response is mediated by *set-6*, *met-2*, *jmjd-1.2*, and *jmjd-3.1*. These genes
456 were dysregulated in the presence of 6PPD-Q, thereby hindering the mt UPR response and
457 increasing *C. elegans*' susceptibility to oxidative damage.^{100,101,103} Consistent exposure to PPDs
458 may prolong the stressful cellular conditions causing continued ROS production. ROS then act
459 as signaling molecules launching an inflammation response.⁹⁹

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460 **How do PPDs affect gene regulation of the inflammatory response?**

461 After consistent PPD exposure elevates ROS, an inflammatory response is generated by
462 the upregulation of proinflammatory genes. These genes code for cytokines which activate the
463 immune response and participate in their own positive feedback mechanism.¹⁰⁰

464 Studies have looked at gene dysregulation of cytokines following 6PPD exposure in
465 mice, zebrafish, and human lung and endometrial epithelial cells.⁷⁰ An upregulation of TNF α
466 confirmed 6PPD causes propagation of the NF- κ B and MAPK inflammation pathways was
467 found. Studies also analyzed gene dysregulation of cytokines following 6PPD-Q exposure in
468 coho salmon, mice, and humans.^{71,72,101,102} A more comprehensive list of dysregulated cytokines
469 and inflammatory pathways were amassed. Similar to organisms treated with 6PPD, 6PPD-Q
470 also caused an upregulation of cytokine TNF α again confirming activation of the NF- κ B and
471 MAPK pathways. Upregulated expression of other cytokines like IL-6, Ripk1, and Fadd indicates
472 JAK-STAT, necrosis, and apoptosis are also prompted. Furthermore, cytokines' ability to create
473 a positive feedback loop may induce chronic inflammation. This has been shown to further
474 disrupt genes regulating metabolism of macromolecules.

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475 **How do PPDs affect gene regulation following the inflammatory response?**

476 6PPD exposure has been well documented to dysregulate lipid metabolism in zebrafish.
477 Multiple studies find an increased expression of genes regulating fatty acid synthesis like *ppary*
478 and *fasn-1*, while there was a decreased expression of genes regulating β -oxidation like *acs-2*
479 and *ech-2*.⁸⁴ Dysregulation of lipid metabolism was further evidenced by an increase in
480 triglyceride and cholesterol levels. In studies treating zebrafish and *C. elegans* with 6PPD-Q,
481 upregulated lipid synthesis and downregulated β -oxidation were also prevalent.

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482 Though there is evidence of other biomolecules, like glucose, with disrupted metabolism,
483 lipids have been by far the most studied.⁹⁴ Consequences may extend beyond gene
484 dysregulation of lipids following continued PPD exposure. As mentioned before, following three
485 weeks of 6PPD-Q exposure, mice displayed disrupted lipid metabolism which culminated in fatty
486 liver disease.⁶⁹ For aquatic organisms known to experience long term exposure of the tire
487 pollutants, this raises a serious risk of hepatotoxicity. Long term damage to the liver may further
488 exacerbate the inflammatory response already prompted by the cellular stress of PPDs.

489 **Cellular Level Interactions of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q**

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490 **4. Metabolomics**

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491 The metabolic fate of 6PPD-Q is still largely unknown. Various *in vivo* and *in vitro*
492 models including, rats, trout, zebrafish, human urine and various liver cell lines, have been used

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493 to discern the Phase I and Phase II metabolites. Phase I metabolites are the first modification of
494 the original compound and Phase II metabolites are the subsequent modifications of Phase I
495 molecules. Depending on the metabolic breakdown across species, Phase II metabolites may
496 originate before Phase I metabolites, or not at all. Across all models the main chemical
497 transformations of 6PPD-Q fall into hydroxylation and oxidation for Phase I, and glucuronidation
498 and sulfation for Phase II metabolites.^{6,12,24,25,27,28} In the rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*)
499 model, the RTL-W1 cell line was used to study liver metabolites of 6PPD-Q. The researchers
500 found the CYP1A, a type of P450 enzyme, is likely responsible for many of the
501 biotransformations of 6PPD-Q.²⁵ One example of the Phase I metabolite in the trout model was
502 hydroxylation of the alkyl side chain. A Phase II metabolite includes glucuronide conjugated
503 transformation products. This particular study inferred the addition of glucuronide and sulfide is
504 thought to increase hydrophilicity which in turn promotes easier elimination.^{24,28} These
505 modifications could contribute to the higher tolerance of 6PPD-Q in rainbow trout.

506 Although there are common metabolites of 6PPD-Q, transformation speeds vary. In mice
507 and zebrafish the metabolism of 6PPD-Q is rapid and occurs within 24 hours of exposure.^{6,12,28}
508 The rapid modification of 6PPD-Q could be the reason behind the higher tolerance in zebrafish
509 and mammalian models. The hydroxylated Phase I metabolites showed no predicted toxic
510 effects when using a modeling system.²⁸ This however needs to be studied more in depth
511 because many Phase II metabolites have not been ruled as non-toxic.⁶ In one study, differences
512 between two human liver cell lines, cancerous HepG2 and noncancerous L02 cells, were found
513 to have differential effects when exposed to 6PPD-Q. Only Phase I metabolites were seen in the
514 L02 cells while both Phase I and II were found in HepG2 cells.²⁷ This difference needs further
515 clarification to see why L02 cells have lower metabolic rates of 6PPD-Q. Since the majority of
516 models studied thus far have similar Phase I modifications, hydroxylation could be used as a
517 potential biomarker for 6PPD-Q exposure.

518 Only one study has investigated the metabolites of 6PPD in zebrafish. Only Phase II
519 metabolites were detected, most likely because of the fast transformation rate of 6PPD. The
520 most common metabolite detected was 4-HDPA, a hydroxylated derivative of 6PPD.⁶ Little
521 information is known about the toxic effects of 4-HDPA. Comparing the results of 6PPD-Q
522 metabolites to those seen in 6PPD metabolic pathways will help determine potential biomarkers
523 for both toxicants.

524 **How do 6PPD and 6PPD-Q affect gene regulation and the inflammatory response?** 525 **Transcriptomics**

526 Researchers have used transcriptomics to further understand the mechanisms by which
527 6PPD and 6PPD-Q induce toxic repercussions. Transcriptomics of organisms known to be in
528 direct contact with 6PPD-Q, such as coho salmon, reveal dysregulation of various transcripts.
529 Dysregulated transcripts encoding proteins that mediate the blood brain barrier and vascular
530 permeability were apparent in a dose dependent manner ranging from 0.1 to 7.2 µg/L of 6PPD-
531 Q.⁴ 6PPD-Q is also thought to dysregulate the immune system as expression of
532 proinflammatory genes *tnfa* and *il1β* were upregulated.⁴

533 In zebrafish, 6PPD and 6PPD-Q cause differential expression of genes related to
534 various signaling pathways, morphological, and physiological effects. This coincides with the
535 phenotypic observations mentioned previously. Exposure of 2.2 mg/L 6PPD altered genes
536 regulating the thyroid signaling pathway. 6PPD also altered expression of genes involved in
537 development of the eye, including *rpe65a* and *opn1lw1*.^{14,18} 6PPD induced lipid accumulation
538 was also verified by an increase in genes regulating lipid synthesis and metabolism.^{94,103}
539 Zebrafish exposed to 6PPD-Q, concentrations ranging from 0.25 to 25 µg/L, experienced
540 dysregulation of genes involved in estrogen signaling in a dose dependent manner. 6PPD-Q
541 also downregulated the expression of *per1a*, *per3*, and *cry3a* involved in circadian rhythm
542 regulation.^{15,16}

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543 In mice, both 6PPD and 6PPD-Q were found to alter hepatic metabolism by upregulated
 544 genes promoting immune responses.⁷⁰ Another study found altered expression of Ripk1, Fadd,
 545 Il-6st, and Il-16 further confirming a change in the immune system.⁷¹

546 One study found *C. elegans*, when exposed to 0.1 to 10 µg/L 6-PPD-Q, significantly
 547 increased their expression of antioxidant genes like *sod-2*, *sod-3*, and *sod-4*.⁷² These findings
 548 were partially backed by another study that found an upregulation of the genes related to the
 549 mitochondrial unfolded proteins response (mt UPR) *atfs-1*, *ubl-5*, and *dve-1* at low
 550 concentrations of 6PPD-Q (0.1 and 1 µg/L).¹⁰⁴ At high concentration the same three genes were
 551 found to be downregulated. The mt UPR indicates stress within the mitochondria and can often
 552 lead to the upregulation of antioxidant enzymes.¹⁰⁵ Lipid accumulation is also found to be
 553 upregulated. This is explained by an increase in transcription of fatty acid synthesis genes *fasn-1*
 554 and *pod-2*, and a decrease in transcription of genes *acs-2* and *ech-2* related to fatty acid
 555 oxidation.⁸⁴ *C. elegans* have lipid accumulation responses to 6PPD-Q similar to those seen in
 556 zebrafish.

557 Most recently, an *in vitro* human endometrial epithelial study demonstrated exposure to
 558 1 µM 6PPD-Q downregulated endometrial receptivity genes, like IL6, whereas 1 to 10 µM 6PPD
 559 upregulated genes, for example, TNFα, involved in inflammation.¹⁰² Collective transcriptomic
 560 profiling indicates a slight trend in the upregulation of immune responses across coho salmon,
 561 mice, and some human epithelial cell lines (Table 24). However, most transcriptomic research
 562 indicates 6PPD and 6PPD-Q enact species dependent effects on gene transcription. Moving
 563 forward, research regarding transcriptomic analysis on various human cell lines may verify or
 564 nullify any overlap between species' transcriptomic mediated 6PPD and 6PPD-Q effects.

566 Table 24. Gene and protein transcription dysregulation in cCoho sSalmon, zZebrafish, mMice,
 567 *C. elegans*, and endometrial epithelial cells and their morphological effects.

	Chemical treated	Genes and proteins Transcripts dysregulated	Alterations to
Coho Salmon	0.1-7.2 µg/L 6PPD-Q	TNFα, il1β, JAM, and ifny	Blood brain barrier, vascular permeability, and inflammation
Zebrafish	2.2 mg/L 6PPD and 0.25-25 µg/L 6PPD-Q and 2.2 mg/L 6PPD	rpe65a, opn1lw1, per1a, per3, and cry3a	Thyroid signaling pathway, eye development, estrogen signaling and circadian rhythm
Mice	10-100 mg/kg 6PPD and 6PPD-Q	Ripk1, Fadd, Il-6st, and Il-16	Immune system, macrophage infiltration, and prostate cancer activation
Endometrial epithelial cells	1-10 µM 6PPD and 1 µM 6PPD-Q	TNFα, IL6, and TGFβ1	Endometrial receptivity and inflammatory responses
<i>C. elegans</i>	10 µg/L 6PPD-Q	atfs-1, ubl-5, dve-1, fasn-1, and pod-2	Mitochondrial unfolded protein response and lipid accumulation

568

569 **3. Protein interactions**

570 To further verify experiments assessing a protein's binding affinity to 6PPD or 6PPD-Q,
 571 researchers are using newly discovered molecular docking software that efficiently predicts a
 572 protein's binding affinity to different chemical compounds. A preliminary *in vitro* assay
 573 demonstrated cytochrome P450's ability to transform 6PPD into 6PPD-Q within human liver
 574 microsomes.⁹⁵ An enzyme inhibition assay then identified CYP1A2 as the most critical

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575 cytochrome involved in the transformation of 6PPD-Q. Molecular docking was then used to
576 confirm 6PPD-Q strongly bound to CYP1A2.²⁴

577 Recently, researchers have prioritized using molecular docking software to confirm
578 6PPD-Q's impact on *C. elegans*. Results indicate 6PPD-Q has a widespread protein-binding
579 ability within *C. elegans*. 6PPD-Q has been found to cause neurodegeneration after activating
580 ion channels MEC-4 and DEG-3.⁸² Molecular docking then confirmed the presence of specific
581 binding sites within MEC-4 and DEG-3. Neurotransmission was further shown to be altered
582 when nematodes introduced to 6PPD-Q had reduced levels of dopamine, serotonin, glutamate,
583 and dopamine. This was confirmed by molecular docking indicating 6PPD-Q binding sites on
584 neurotransmitter synthesis proteins.⁸¹

585 Despite 6PPD-Q being a related ozonized counterpart of 6PPD, research often shows
586 stark contrast regarding the effects of both chemicals. 6PPD bound to human serum albumin
587 (HSA) resulted in activation of the esterase activity whereas 6PPD-Q binding to HSA inhibited
588 its esterase activity. Molecular docking was used to investigate this dichotomy. Software
589 confirmed 6PPD and 6PPD-Q each interacted with amino acid residues on HSA. The higher
590 binding affinity of HSA to 6PPD was a result of 6PPD's more negative surface potential.⁹⁶ The
591 difference in chemical structure may be the key to understanding how these toxicants interact *in*
592 *vitro* and *in vivo*.

593 Some studies are relying entirely on molecular docking software to evaluate 6PPD and
594 6PPD-Q's ability to bind to specific proteins.^{97,98} While molecular docking has been proven to be
595 an increasingly valuable resource, the importance of continuing to include experimental data
596 confirming the predicted binding properties of a protein *in vitro* is integral to furthering the 6PPD
597 and 6PPD-Q research domain.

598 4. Epigenetics

599 — As of March 2025, only one study has linked epigenetic changes in *C. elegans* to
600 exposure to 6PPD-Q. When exposed, *C. elegans* can employ the mt UPR to ensure the
601 mitochondria continues to function at a normal capacity.¹⁰⁶ Under stress conditions the mt UPR
602 is employed in nematodes using genes *atfs-1*, *ubl-5* and *dve-1*. These genes are under control
603 by upstream histone methyltransferases, *set-6* and *met-2*, and histone demethylases, *jmjd-1.2*
604 and *jmjd-3.1*. Upon treatment of 6PPD-Q at 1 and 10 µg/L, *met-2* and *set-6* exhibited an
605 increase in mRNA levels while *jmjd-1.2* and *jmjd-3.1* showed a decrease in mRNA levels.¹⁰⁴ The
606 change in expression of these genes lead to a decrease in activation of the mt UPR response
607 making the nematodes more susceptible to the toxic effects of 6PPD-Q.¹⁰⁴ This study only
608 scratched the surface of epigenetic changes within one species. Additional studies investigating
609 6PPD and 6PPD-Q in different model organisms, site specific DNA methylation, histone
610 modification and transgenerational epigenetic effects will give better insight to the long-term
611 effects of these environmental pollutants.

612 How do 6PPD and 6PPD-Q affect the inflammatory response? 5. Reactive Oxygen Species 613 (ROS, inflammation and lipid accumulation combined)

614 Wide scale research has been done regarding 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's ability to increase
615 oxidative stress within a cell as indicated by elevation of reactive oxygen species (ROS).
616 Commonly formed ROS often include superoxide anions, hydroxyl radicals, and hydrogen
617 peroxide.¹⁰⁷ 6PPD increased ROS levels in embryonic, larval, and adult zebrafish.^{9,13,14,108-110}
618 Following studies focusing on aquatic animals at high risk of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q exposure,
619 researchers have also studied plants and algae at similarly high risk of exposure. 6PPD was
620 found to increase oxidative stress in microalgae whereas 6PPD-Q increased ROS levels in
621 various aquatic plants.¹¹¹⁻¹¹³ Aquatic plant studies also indicate 6PPD-Q exposure results in
622 more oxidative stress than 6PPD. Many studies found 6PPD-Q also induce ROS within human
623 cell lines like L02 and HepG2 as well as *C. elegans* and mice.^{27,73,77,83,114,115}

624 Following increased levels of ROS, antioxidant proteins may mitigate the harmful effects
625 of oxidative stress. Studies have found an increased expression of antioxidant proteins like

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626 SOD-2, SOD-3, and SOD-4 following PPD exposure as seen in Figure 32.⁷⁷⁻⁹⁸ 6PPD and 6PPD-
627 Q also directly increase the activity of antioxidant proteins.¹¹⁶ RNA interference, RNAi, further
628 confirmed the importance of antioxidant species following PPD exposure. SOD-3 is a common
629 downstream target of DAF-16, an oxidative stress response protein.⁷⁹ RNAi of *daf-16* resulting
630 in increased susceptibility to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's production of ROS because of decreased
631 activation of antioxidant proteins.^{86,104,114} RNAi of SOD-2 and SOD-3 also increased *C. elegans*'
632 susceptibility to ROS.⁸⁰ These results indicate 6PPD and 6PPD-Q directly influence the
633 oxidative stress levels in *C. elegans*. Continuing to focus on 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's effect on ROS
634 levels will help link these pathways to cellular damage and inflammation pathways.

635 **6. Inflammatory Response**

636 Extensive research has been done regarding 6PPD and 6PPD-Q induced inflammation
637 in mammals. One study found at doses of 10 and 100 µg/kg 6PPD-Q elevated common
638 cytokines TNF-α, IL-1, and IL-6 levels in mice.⁷² Cytokines are crucial signaling molecules in the
639 inflammatory pathway.¹¹⁷ 6PPD-Q was found to specifically induce neuroinflammation in mice
640 by increasing TNF-α, IL-6, IL-1β levels and microglia.⁷³ Inflammation within mice lungs following
641 6PPD-Q exposure resulted in increased cytokine levels as well as increased expression of
642 genes regulating inflammation responses like *Ripk1*, *Fadd*, *Il-6st*, and *Il-16*.⁷⁴ 6PPD and 6PPD-
643 Q also cause inflammation within human lung cells as both PPDs induce an increase in
644 proinflammatory cytokine release.¹¹⁸ Another study found human endometrial epithelial cells
645 upregulated TNFα cytokine expression following exposure to 6PPD and upregulated LIF
646 cytokine expression following 6PPD-Q exposure.¹⁰²

647 Studies have also found increased inflammation in aquatic species. In coho salmon,
648 6PPD-Q upregulated the expression of proinflammatory molecules TNFα and il1β.⁴ In zebrafish,
649 6PPD caused dysregulation of the inflammatory response as indicated by a significant decrease
650 in TNFα, IL-6 and IL-10 gene expression. An inflammation response was still triggered by 6PPD
651 as the toxicant increased the expression of NF-κB pathway genes regulating fast, acute
652 inflammation. Current research indicates the effects of 6PPD, and 6PPD-Q often manifest in
653 upregulation of inflammatory pathways as well as proinflammatory cytokine release.¹⁰⁹

654 **7. Lipid Accumulation**

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Figure 32. Comprehensive overview of known interactions of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q (created using BioRender.com).

Conclusion

Future Trends in 6PPD and 6PPD-Q Research

Through this literature search we aimed to summarize the toxicological effects of PPDs, 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, on aquatic and terrestrial organisms and point out the major gaps that need to be addressed as regulations are developed. After compiling data covering *in vivo* and *in vitro* models, it is clear that 6PPD and 6PPD-Q have some overlapping toxic effects but also some distinct characteristics. Because the discovery of PPDs as an environmental toxicant is relatively new, integrating interdisciplinary research methods will help increase knowledge and help inform global regulations. We specifically recommend focusing on discerning the toxic mechanisms of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q through the following routes:

This holistic review summarized 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's toxicological effects on aquatic and terrestrial organisms highly susceptible to these tire pollutants. Terrestrial mammals and invertebrates were also included for comparison. With the expectation of providing insight to common intracellular pathways and mechanisms targeted, we focused on outlining the fate of PPD metabolites, protein interactions, and gene dysregulation leading to inflammatory responses, metabolomics, transcriptomics, protein interactions and epigenetics. Despite the breadth in studies considered for this review, major research gaps persist hindering the expedition of environmental regulations. Few connections between species-dependent mechanisms and pathways were inferred. A more comprehensive scope would benefit our mission of providing a thorough commentary, however, we find the limited information regarding specific research areas like protein interactions and epigenetics can be attributed to the

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683 relatively new spotlight on the toxicantn. Alternatively, numerous conflicting discoveries,
684 specifically morphological changes and mortality rates within zebrafish, were discussed. With
685 6PPD and 6PPD-Q recently emerging as hazardous environmental pollutants, considerable
686 research gaps regarding the toxicantns require further attention (Figure 43). Based on the
687 cumulative data presented in this review we have compiled a list of possible future research
688 trends that may contribute to the creation of formal regulations:

689 **1. EPA regulation.** As of today, there are no EPA regulations stating the maximum level
690 6PPD or 6PPD-Q can reach in the environment. Because the toxicity of these tire antiozonants
691 has only recently been discovered there is little to no research on the environmental effects. The
692 EPA is working to provide funding for tire wear emissions, the fate of 6PPD, where it
693 accumulates, and toxicology studies.^{29,30} As well as providing funding for continuous research,
694 the EPA is also spreading awareness of the possible pollutant to many native American tribes.
695 These tribes rely heavily on salmon populations to sustain their people. Therefore, 6PPD and
696 6PPD-Q, which are known to be toxic to a variety of salmon species, threaten both animals and
697 humans alike. Additional trends in research listed below ~~should be explored to expedite~~ may
698 contribute to expediting the EPA regulation process.

699 **1. Transgenerational studies. Expansion upon consequences throughout organisms'
700 lifecycle.** As seen with coho salmon, the tolerance level, although small, increased
701 throughout the lifecycle. Determining lifecycle tolerance differences for robust species,
702 sensitive species, and any in between will help environmentalists be well informed when
703 implementing PPD regulations for various habitats.

704 **2.** Across the many studies presented the tolerance levels for PPDs varies greatly.
705 Typically, the species are categorized as tolerant or sensitive but the exotoxicology is usually
706 more nuanced. of organismal response to 6PPD-Q two main categories are apparent: tolerant
707 and sensitive species. Although some species fall somewhere between very sensitive and
708 highly tolerant, focusing on the comparison of robust species with highly affected species may
709 be the key to uncovering PPDs toxic mechanisms and detoxification pathways. Tolerant species
710 have a much higher threshold of 6PPD-Q they can endure before showing toxicity effects, while
711 sensitive species exhibit stress responses, like elevated breathing rate, at low concentrations.⁹⁰
712 Additional categorization of species as tolerant or sensitive is necessary. For
713 example, Therefore, focusing on the differences between coho salmon, a sensitive species and
714 zebrafish, a tolerant species, could reveal specific lifestage tolerance differences. Currently the
715 knowledgebase surrounding coho salmon and zebrafish focus on embryonic forms and juvenile
716 life stages.^{2,4,8,10,13,14,16,18,68} Moving forward implementation of studies comparing physiological
717 effects induced in all life stages of zebrafish, other fish species, and coho salmon would provide
718 a comprehensive understanding and interesting comparison between species. Addition of all life
719 stages may aid in the discovery of tolerance mechanisms or certain species becoming more
720 tolerant as they age.

721 **2. Female model organisms.** 6PPD and 6PPD-Q have been identified to disrupt
722 reproductive health in mice. The main focus has been on male mice and
723 spermatogenesis. This discovery is pertinent, however investigating the effects of PPDs
724 on female reproductive health is of equal importance. Additionally, any discoveries
725 associated with reproductive health may also be linked to transgenerational effects.

726 **3. Epigenetics.** Another route to address transgenerational research gaps is epigenetic
727 studies. This field gives insight into gene alterations at the individual level as well as
728 possible explanations for inheritance of mutations and exposure impacts.

729 **3-4. Fungal cell toxicology and metagenomics. Toxicological effects on fungal
730 cells.** Fungi are an integral aspect of water ecosystems. Fungal communities give vital
731 information about the health of the ecosystem they reside in. No studies have ventured
732 into the effects of PPDs on fungal cells. This could be an interesting approach to discern
733 ~~the ecosystem and~~ effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. As fungal cells are single-celled

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eukaryotes, cell trafficking and protein interactions can easily be studied. Implementation of yeast studies opens the door to faster turnaround of data acquisition as well as multi-faceted research approaches, such as metabolomics, metagenomics, transcriptomics, and bioaccumulation.

Fertility across sexespecies and transgenerational effects. 6PPD and 6PPD-Q have been identified as ~~toxicanstoxicants~~ns to reproductive health in mice. The main focus has been on male mice and the disruption of spermatogenesis.⁷⁰⁻⁷⁶ Although male reproduction is important, it is critical to also investigate the effects of PPDs on female reproductive health. Therefore, it would be highly beneficial to study the impacts of female fertility and how PPDs affect future generations. These transgeneration effects may link to potential epigenetic changes across species further expanding the tire toxicantn research field.

4. Toxicological effects on fungal cells. Fungi are an integral aspect of water ecosystems. Fungal communities give vital information about the health of the ecosystem they reside in. No studies have ventured into the effects of PPDs on fungal cells. This could be an interesting approach to discern the ecosystem and effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q on fungal ecosystems. As fungal cells are single-celled eukaryotes, cell trafficking and protein interactions can easily be studied. Implementation of yeast studies opens the door to faster turnaround of data acquisition as well as multi-faceted research approaches, such as metabolomics, transcriptomics, and bioaccumulation.

— **Fate of metabolites and their interactions *in vivo*.** A preliminary foundation of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q metabolites has been formed. Taking the available information and continually building upon the metabolic fate and toxicity of PPD transformation products is essential to determining exposure biomarkers. Ultimately, uncovering the general pathways used to metabolize 6PPD and 6PPD-Q will aid in our understanding of their mechanistic impact.

5. Information regarding the Phase I and Phase II metabolites of 6PPD-Q has progressed rapidly. As PPDs become more prominent in the environment, detailing the fate and toxicity of these metabolites should be a top priority. Creating potential pathways of biotransformations and fates of metabolites is heavily important in pinning down potential biological markers to be used in exposure studies. Additionally, studies covering the metabolites of 6PPD are few in number. The biological markers for both chemicals may be different, even though 6PPD-Q is a derivative of 6PPD. Ultimately, understanding the similarities and differences between the breakdown of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q will help aid our understanding of species-specific detoxification mechanisms.

6. Metagenomics approach. Another interesting trend in future research is the implementation of metagenomics. Since 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are prominent water pollutants, analyzing the diversity of microorganisms in waterways with high levels of tire pollutants is necessary. Comparison of waterways, polluted and non-polluted, would provide differences in microbial community demographics. Additionally, microorganisms provide valuable information about water quality. Some microbes also have the ability to detoxify harmful materials. Using metagenomics to identify detoxifying bacteria present in polluted water may lead to potential bioremediation of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q using bacterial species.

7.5. PPD6PPD and 6PPD-Q effects on cancer cell lines. There is limited knowledge of how 6PPD and 6PPD-Q interact with cancerous cells.²⁷ Using cancer cells as a model system is advantageous because of the ease of culturing and wide availability. Since cancerous cell lines are immortalized, ~~makingpreparing~~ long term studies investigating toxicological effects ~~is made~~ possible. Additionally, cancer cells offer great insight to processes such as programmed cell death, viability and oxidative stress. These assessments are essential to uncovering the mechanisms behind PPD toxicity and serve as a good model to investigate remediation effects of different chemicals.

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785 **8. — Proteomics.** This area of study will help link the information presented in transcriptomic
786 and metabolomic research. Protein interaction studies have been a large proponent of
787 discerning the mechanism of action of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, however little is known about the
788 changes in protein structure when in the presence of PPDs.

789 **Epigenetics knowledge expansion.** Another route to address transgenerational research gaps
790 is epigenetic studies. This field gives insight into gene alterations at the individual level as well
791 as possible explanations for inheritance of mutations and exposure impacts.

792 **9. —** Epigenetics has become more common in toxicology studies, however, as of March
793 2025, there is only one study investigating epigenetic effects of 6PPD-Q.¹⁰⁴ Shifting focus from
794 transcriptomic evaluation to study the epigenetic effects of both PPDs covered in this
795 commentary could yield novel research. Add linker to make transgenerational research effects
796 more robust. Assessing the transgenerational effects of PPDs on DNA would be highly
797 informative and give better insight into how these toxic chemicals work. Epigenetic changes
798 may be one reason as to why 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are so toxic.

799 **6. Single-cell sequencing (SCS).** We discussed ~~various~~ various studies using different model
800 organisms and cell lines ~~have been published~~ showing toxic effects of PPDs. However,
801 effects on different organs have yet to be investigated. Single-cell sequencing will
802 remedy this by giving insight into how different ~~organ~~ cells react to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q
803 exposure. This methodology can be used to illustrate the potential toxicological effects
804 across organ systems. As 6PPD and 6PPD-Q research progresses, single-cell
805 sequencing should be one of the next steps.

806 **10. Coexposure of environmental toxicants.** 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are not isolated
807 toxicants. The likelihood of multiple toxic chemicals, like PHAs and metaloids,
808 interacting is high. Investigating coexposure in as many model organisms as possible
809 would give insightful information on how different toxicants interact synergistically,
810 antagonistically, or not at all.

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813
 814 Figure 43. Summary of future trends in 6PPD and 6PPD-Q studies (created using
 815 BioRender.com).
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817 All the above-mentioned future research trends are equally important in advancing
818 scientific understanding of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. Collectively, each area of emphasis will bridge
819 the gaps in knowledge and provide a more thorough understanding of tire pollutant impacts.
820 Eventually, this ground-breaking research will help formulate EPA-regulations and combat the
821 toxic effects of PPDs.

822
823

824 **Author Contributions**

825 E.B.: writing-original draft preparation, review, editing; M.M.: writing-original draft preparation,
826 review, editing; K.K.: review, editing, and supervision. All authors have read and agreed to the
827 published version of the manuscript.

828

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832

833 **Disclosure of interest**

834 The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

835

836 **Data Availability Statement**

837 Data sharing is not applicable as no new data was created or analyzed in this review.

838

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844

845 Abbreviations

846 6PPD: (N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-phenyl-p-phenylenediamine)

847 6PPD-Q: N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-phenyl-p-phenylenediamine-quinone

848 USEPA: United States Environmental Protection agency

849 PPD: p-Phenylenediamine

850 CEPA: Canadian Environmental Protection Agency

851 REACH: Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals

852 NIH: National Institute of Health

853 LC50: Lethal concentration 50

854 UPLC-QE: Ultra performance liquid chromatography - Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap mass
855 spectrometry

856 BPM: beats per minute

857 IVF: *in vitro* fertilization

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858 TNF α : Tumor Necrosis Factor - α
859 IL-1: Interleukin-1
860 IL-10: Interleukin-10
861 IL-6: Interleukin-6
862 *Il1b*: interleukin 1 β gene
863 *per1a*: Period circadian clock 1 a gene
864 *per3*: period circadian regulator 3
865 *cry3a*: cryptochrome circadian regulator 3a
866 Ripk1: Receptor-interacting serine/threonine-protein kinase 1
867 Fadd: Fas-associated death domain
868 Il-6st: Interleukin 6 Cytokine Family Signal Transducer
869 Il-16: Interleukin-16
870 *SOD-2*: superoxide dismutase 2 gene
871 *SOD-3*: superoxide dismutase 3 gene
872 *SOD-4*: superoxide dismutase 4 gene
873 ROS: Reactive oxygen species
874 MASLD: metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease
875 BMI: Body mass index
876 PBDE: polybrominated diphenyl ethers
877 PCB: polychlorinated biphenyls
878 Ni: Nickle
879 Cu: Copper
880 ADI: acceptable daily intake
881 TDI: tolerable daily intake
882 ILCM: interlamellar cell mass
883 L02: human liver hepatocyte
884 HepG2: Hepatocellular carcinoma

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885 TP: transformation product

886 Mt UPR: mitochondrial unfold protein response

887 *atfs-1*: Activating Transcription Factor associated with Stress-1

888 *ubl-5*: ubiquitin-like protein 5

889 *dve-1*: homeobox transcriptional regulator

890 *fasn-1*: Fatty acid synthase 1 gene

891 *pod-2*: Acetyl-CoA Carboxylase gene

892 p450: cytochrome p450 protein

893 CYP1A2: Cytochrome p450 1A2

894 CYP3A: Cytochrome p450 3A

895 2C19: Cytochrome p450 2C19

896 ANF: α -naphthoflavone

897 BAS-1: cytochrome p450 superfamily protein

898 GRB-10: globin like protein 10

899 JAK2: Janus kinase 2

900 SOD: superoxide dismutase

901 HSA: Human Serum Albumin

902 NF- κ B: Nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells

903 PAH: polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

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1344 **Supplemental Information**

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1346 **Supplemental Figure 1. World map detailing locations that have detected 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.**
 1347 **(created using Biorender.com)**

1348 **Supplemental Table 1. Countries with 6PPD and/or 6PPD-Q detected in local samples.**

Country	Location of Sample Site	Chemical	References
Argentina	Buenos Aires	6PPD-Q	[35]
Australia	Queensland (Brisbane River)	6PPD-Q	[36,37]

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<u>Brazil</u>	<u>São Paulo</u>	<u>6PPD-Q</u>	<u>[35]</u>
<u>Canada</u>	<u>Southern Ontario (Don River and Highland Creek) and Toronto</u>	<u>6PPD-Q</u>	<u>[35,38-40]</u>
<u>Chile</u>	<u>Santiago</u>	<u>6PPD-Q</u>	<u>[35]</u>
<u>China</u>	<u>Guangzhou (Liuxi River and Guanghua Basin), South China (Greater Bay Area), Guangdong (Pearl River and Dongjiang river), Zhejiang (Zhujiang river and Jiaojiang River), Yangtze River, Taiyuan, Zhengzhou, Shanghai, Nanjing, Hangzhou, and Hong Kong</u>	<u>6PPD and 6PPD-Q</u>	<u>[24,41-52]</u>
<u>Colombia</u>	<u>Bogota</u>	<u>6PPD-Q</u>	<u>[35]</u>
<u>Germany</u>	<u>Leipzig Saxony</u>	<u>6PPD and 6PPD-Q</u>	<u>[53-56]</u>
<u>India</u>	<u>Kolkata and New Delhi</u>	<u>6PPD-Q</u>	<u>[35]</u>
<u>Japan</u>	<u>Tokyo</u>	<u>6PPD-Q</u>	<u>[35,57]</u>
<u>Nigeria</u>	<u>Lagos</u>	<u>6PPD-Q</u>	<u>[35]</u>
<u>Poland</u>	<u>Warsaw</u>	<u>6PPD-Q</u>	<u>[35]</u>
<u>Spain</u>	<u>Madrid</u>	<u>6PPD-Q</u>	<u>[35]</u>
<u>USA</u>	<u>California (San Francisco Bay), Colorado, Georgia, Kansas, Michigan, Minnesota, Mississippi (Oxford), New York, North Carolina, Oklahoma, Oregon, Texas, Virginia, and Washington (Tacoma)</u>	<u>6PPD-Q</u>	<u>[35,58-61]</u>

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Supplemental Table 2. Common concentrations of 6PPD* and 6PPD-Q* listed as micrograms per liter (µg/L) and corresponding conversion to nanomolar (nM).

<u>6PPD (µg/L)</u>	<u>6PPD (nM)</u>	<u>6PPD-Q (µg/L)</u>	<u>6PPD-Q (nM)</u>
<u>0.1</u>	<u>0.370</u>	<u>0.1</u>	<u>0.340</u>
<u>5</u>	<u>1.86</u>	<u>5</u>	<u>1.68</u>
<u>10</u>	<u>3.73</u>	<u>10</u>	<u>3.35</u>
<u>50</u>	<u>18.6</u>	<u>50</u>	<u>16.8</u>
<u>100</u>	<u>37.3</u>	<u>100</u>	<u>33.5</u>

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1352

1353
1354
1355

500

186

500

167.6

1000

373

1000

335

*Based on molar masses 6PPD, 268.4 g/mol and 6PPD-Q, 298.4 g/mol

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